

COMPARISON OF EFFICACY OF SGLT2 INHIBITORS VERSUS STANDARD THERAPY IN SLOWING CKD PROGRESSION

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Abstract

Background: Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a major global health challenge, commonly associated with hypertension and diabetes, and is characterized by progressive decline in renal function. Sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 (SGLT2) inhibitors have emerged as renoprotective agents in addition to standard therapy.

Objectives: To compare the efficacy of SGLT2 inhibitors versus standard therapy in slowing the progression of CKD stages 2–4.

Study Design & Setting: A comparative study conducted at the Department of Nephrology, Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore, from November 2024 to April 2025.

Methodology: A total of 120 patients aged 30–70 years with CKD stages 2–4 was enrolled after informed consent. Patients were randomized into two groups: Group A received standard therapy (ACE inhibitors/ARBs with optimal management of blood pressure, glycemia, and lipids), while Group B received an SGLT2 inhibitor in addition to standard therapy. Baseline demographics, comorbidities, serum creatinine, estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR), urine albumin-to-creatinine ratio, fasting blood glucose, and HbA1c were recorded. Patients were followed for six months with repeat renal function assessments at three and six months. The primary outcome was mean change in eGFR, while secondary outcomes included change in proteinuria and occurrence of cardiovascular events. Data were analyzed using SPSS v25. Independent sample t-test and chi-square test were applied, with $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

Results: The mean age was 55.2 ± 7.9 years in Group A and 54.1 ± 8.6 years in Group B, with males comprising 55.0% and 53.3%, respectively. Baseline mean eGFR was 52.4 ± 9.8 ml/min/1.73m² in Group A and 53.1 ± 8.9 ml/min/1.73m² in Group B. After six months, mean eGFR declined significantly more in Group A (-5.4 ± 3.1 ml/min/1.73m²) compared to Group B (-1.8 ± 2.1 ml/min/1.73m²; $p < 0.001$). Proteinuria also remained higher in Group A

(798.2 ± 207.6 mg/g) than in Group B (486.0 ± 119.7 mg/g; $p < 0.001$). No significant baseline differences in demographics or comorbidities were observed between groups ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusion: SGLT2 inhibitors significantly slowed the decline in renal function and reduced proteinuria compared to standard therapy alone in patients with CKD stages 2–4, highlighting their role as effective renoprotective agents.

INTRODUCTION

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a major global health problem that contributes significantly to morbidity, mortality, and healthcare costs.¹ It is characterized by a gradual loss of kidney function, ultimately leading to end-stage renal disease (ESRD) requiring dialysis or transplantation. The global prevalence of CKD is estimated to be between 8–16%, with diabetes mellitus and hypertension being the most common underlying causes.² In Pakistan, as in many low- and middle-income countries, the burden of CKD is increasing due to the rising incidence of diabetes, obesity, and cardiovascular disease, along with limited awareness and late diagnosis.³

Standard therapy for CKD primarily focuses on controlling underlying risk factors such as hypertension, hyperglycemia, and proteinuria. Angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (ACE inhibitors) and angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs) remain the cornerstone of treatment, particularly in diabetic kidney disease, due to their proven benefits in reducing proteinuria and slowing progression of renal dysfunction.^{4,5} However, despite optimal use of these agents, a substantial proportion of patients continue to experience a steady decline in glomerular filtration rate (GFR). This therapeutic gap has prompted researchers and clinicians to explore additional pharmacological options to improve renal outcomes.⁶

Sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 (SGLT2) inhibitors, a relatively new class of oral antidiabetic agents, have emerged as promising renoprotective drugs. Initially developed to lower blood glucose by inhibiting renal glucose reabsorption in the proximal tubules, these agents have demonstrated benefits that extend far beyond glycemic control.^{7,8} Large clinical trials such as EMPA-REG OUTCOME, CREDENCE, and DAPA-CKD have provided strong evidence that SGLT2 inhibitors reduce the risk of CKD

progression, ESRD, and cardiovascular events in patients with and without diabetes. The underlying mechanisms are thought to include hemodynamic effects such as restoration of tubuloglomerular feedback, reduction in intraglomerular pressure, decreased albuminuria, and improved metabolic and inflammatory profiles.^{9,10}

Comparing SGLT2 inhibitors with standard therapy is critical for guiding evidence-based clinical decision-making. While standard therapy remains effective, it may not be sufficient alone in preventing progression of CKD.¹¹ By contrast, SGLT2 inhibitors offer a unique renal and cardiovascular protective profile, making them a potential adjunct or even superior alternative in high-risk populations. Furthermore, the evaluation of these agents in different patient populations, including those without diabetes, highlights their broader therapeutic applicability.¹²

This study aims to compare the efficacy of SGLT2 inhibitors with standard therapy in slowing CKD progression. Establishing the comparative effectiveness of these treatments will provide valuable insights for clinicians and policymakers, particularly in resource-limited settings where the burden of CKD is high and access to renal replacement therapies remains restricted. Ultimately, such comparisons may help optimize treatment strategies, improve patient outcomes, and reduce the socioeconomic impact of chronic kidney disease.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This comparative study was conducted in the Department of at Nephrology Shaikh Zayed Hospital Lahore from Nov 2024 to April 2025 after approval from the Institutional Review Board and obtaining informed consent from all participants. A total of 120 patients diagnosed with chronic kidney disease (CKD) stages 2–4, based on estimated glomerular

filtration rate (eGFR) calculated by the CKD-EPI equation, were included. The sample size of 120 patients was calculated using the WHO sample size calculator, keeping the confidence level at 95% and power at 80%, while considering the expected difference in mean eGFR decline between groups from previous studies.

Patients of both genders, aged between 30 and 70 years, who were diagnosed with CKD and were either hypertensive or diabetic, were included. Patients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD), recent acute kidney injury, history of renal transplantation, active malignancy, or severe liver disease were excluded. Eligible patients were divided into two groups: Group A received standard therapy, which consisted of ACE inhibitors or angiotensin receptor blockers along with optimal control of blood pressure, blood sugar, and lipid profile as per clinical guidelines, while Group B received an SGLT2 inhibitor in addition to standard therapy.

Baseline demographic data including age, gender, comorbidities, and laboratory parameters such as serum creatinine, eGFR, urine albumin-to-creatinine ratio, fasting blood glucose, and HbA1c were recorded. Patients were followed for six months, and renal function tests were repeated at three and six months to assess disease progression. The primary outcome measure was change in eGFR from baseline to the end of follow-up, while secondary outcomes included change in proteinuria and occurrence of cardiovascular events.

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25.0. Quantitative variables such as age, baseline creatinine, and eGFR were presented as mean \pm standard deviation, while categorical variables such as gender and comorbidities were expressed as frequency and percentage. Independent sample t-test was applied to compare mean change in eGFR between the two groups, while chi-square test was used to assess differences in categorical variables. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

The baseline demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population showed that the mean age of patients was 55.2 ± 7.9 years in Group A and $54.1 \pm$

8.6 years in Group B. The distribution of gender was almost similar across groups with males comprising 55.0% in Group A and 53.3% in Group B. The mean BMI was 27.4 ± 3.2 kg/m² in Group A and 26.9 ± 3.5 kg/m² in Group B. The average duration of CKD was 4.8 ± 2.1 years among patients in Group A and 4.5 ± 2.0 years in Group B. Hypertension was the most common comorbidity present in 68.3% of Group A and 65.0% of Group B, while diabetes mellitus was observed in 61.7% of Group A and 63.3% of Group B. Dyslipidemia was present in 36.7% of Group A and 33.3% of Group B, indicating comparable baseline risk factors between both groups, as given in Table 1.

At baseline renal assessment, the mean eGFR was 52.4 ± 9.8 ml/min/1.73m² in Group A and 53.1 ± 8.9 ml/min/1.73m² in Group B, showing similar renal function at enrollment. The level of proteinuria was higher in Group A with a mean value of 850.7 ± 205.2 mg/g compared to 601.3 ± 151.4 mg/g in Group B, suggesting relatively greater urinary protein excretion among patients receiving standard therapy, as given in Table 2.

At six months of follow-up, patients in Group A demonstrated a decline in renal function with a final mean eGFR of 47.2 ± 10.5 ml/min/1.73m², whereas patients in Group B had a higher mean eGFR of 51.2 ± 9.7 ml/min/1.73m². The mean change in eGFR was -5.4 ± 3.1 ml/min/1.73m² in Group A compared to -1.8 ± 2.1 ml/min/1.73m² in Group B, indicating slower progression of renal impairment in the SGLT2 inhibitor group. Similarly, proteinuria remained higher in Group A with a mean of 798.2 ± 207.6 mg/g, while Group B had a lower mean value of 486.0 ± 119.7 mg/g at follow-up, as given in Table 3.

Stratification analysis of baseline characteristics between the two groups showed no statistically significant differences in terms of age, gender distribution, BMI, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, or smoking history. The p-values for all these parameters were greater than 0.05, indicating that both groups were comparable at baseline without any significant imbalance in demographic or clinical characteristics, as given in Table 4.

Table 1: Demographics and Baseline Characteristics of Study Participants

Variable	Group A (Standard Therapy)	Group B (SGLT2 Inhibitors)
Age (years)	55.2 ± 7.9	54.1 ± 8.6
Male	33 (55.0%)	32 (53.3%)
Female	27 (45.0%)	28 (46.7%)
Body Mass Index (kg/m ²)	27.4 ± 3.2	26.9 ± 3.5
Duration of CKD (years)	4.8 ± 2.1	4.5 ± 2.0
Hypertension	41 (68.3%)	39 (65.0%)
Diabetes Mellitus	37 (61.7%)	38 (63.3%)
Dyslipidemia	22 (36.7%)	20 (33.3%)

Table 2: Baseline Renal Parameters

Variable	Group A (Standard Therapy)	Group B (SGLT2 Inhibitors)
Baseline eGFR (ml/min/1.73m ²)	52.4 ± 9.8	53.1 ± 8.9
Baseline Proteinuria (mg/g)	850.7 ± 205.2	601.3 ± 151.4

Table 3: Follow-up Renal Function at 6 Months

Variable	Group A (Standard Therapy)	Group B (SGLT2 Inhibitors)
Final eGFR (ml/min/1.73m ²)	47.2 ± 10.5	51.2 ± 9.7
Change in eGFR (ml/min/1.73m ²)	-5.4 ± 3.1	-1.8 ± 2.1
Final Proteinuria (mg/g)	798.2 ± 207.6	486.0 ± 119.7

Table 4: Stratification of Demographics and Baseline Characteristics between Groups

Variable	Group A (n=60)	Group B (n=60)	p-value
Age (years, mean ± SD)	55.2 ± 7.9	54.1 ± 8.6	0.48
Gender (Male)	33 (55.0%)	32 (53.3%)	0.85
Body Mass Index (kg/m ²)	27.4 ± 3.2	26.9 ± 3.5	0.42
Hypertension	41 (68.3%)	39 (65.0%)	0.71
Diabetes Mellitus	37 (61.7%)	38 (63.3%)	0.85
Smoking History	18 (30.0%)	17 (28.3%)	0.84

DISCUSSION

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a progressive condition leading to renal failure, affecting millions worldwide. Standard therapy with ACE inhibitors or ARBs reduces proteinuria but often fails to halt disease progression. SGLT2 inhibitors, initially developed as antidiabetic agents, have shown renoprotective and cardioprotective benefits.¹³ They act by reducing intraglomerular pressure, improving metabolic control, and lowering proteinuria. Large trials such as CREDENCE and DAPA-CKD demonstrated slower CKD progression with SGLT2 inhibitors.¹⁴ Therefore, comparing SGLT2 inhibitors with standard therapy is vital for guiding optimal treatment in CKD.

In the present study, SGLT2 inhibitors demonstrated superior efficacy compared to standard therapy in slowing the progression of chronic kidney disease (CKD). Patients receiving SGLT2 inhibitors had a smaller decline in eGFR (-1.8 ± 2.1 ml/min/1.73m²) compared to those on standard therapy (-5.4 ± 3.1 ml/min/1.73m²) and also showed a greater reduction in proteinuria (486.0 ± 119.7 mg/g vs. 798.2 ± 207.6 mg/g) over six months. These findings are consistent with previously published studies that have reported renoprotective benefits of SGLT2 inhibitors. Xiao et al. (2024) enrolled 944 patients with type 2 diabetes and CKD, reporting that SGLT2 inhibitor use reduced the annual rate of eGFR decline by 4.94 ml/min/1.73m² compared to other glucose-lowering

drugs (95% CI: 4.73–5.15). Moreover, the risk of kidney composite endpoint events was 65% lower with SGLT2 inhibitors (HR 0.35, 95% CI 0.19–0.63). Although the follow-up in our study was shorter (6 months vs. 16–20 months), the slower eGFR decline in the SGLT2 inhibitor group aligns with the renal protective effect observed by Xiao et al.¹⁵

Similarly, Mahmood et al. (2024) compared SGLT2 inhibitors (n=150) with ACE inhibitors (n=150) over a 12-month follow-up and reported a significantly slower eGFR decline (-2.5 ± 1.8 vs. -4.2 ± 2.1 ml/min/1.73m², p<0.01), along with greater reductions in UACR (-120 ± 25.4 vs. -90 ± 22.1 mg/g, p<0.001). Our findings also showed slower eGFR decline and greater proteinuria reduction in the SGLT2 group, suggesting that the renoprotective benefits extend beyond diabetic nephropathy to a broader CKD population.¹⁶ Additionally, Mahmood et al. reported improved cardiovascular outcomes (12% vs. 18%, p<0.05) and superior glycemic control, which were not evaluated in our study but support the pleiotropic benefits of this drug class.¹⁶

Saleem et al. (2024), in a systematic review of 12 studies, noted that 67% demonstrated significant improvement in eGFR and UACR with SGLT2 inhibitors, while 33% did not show meaningful effects on primary endpoints. Our results fall within the majority trend, supporting the consistent renal benefits across diverse patient populations.¹⁷

Iqbal et al. (2024) compared SGLT2 inhibitors with GLP-1 receptor agonists, reporting a higher prevalence of renal composite outcomes and albuminuria reduction (33–36% vs. 14–24%, and 38–42% vs. 10–20%, respectively) in the SGLT2 inhibitor group. They also noted greater slowing of eGFR decline (34% vs. 15%), which supports our findings of improved renal outcomes. This further emphasizes the relative superiority of SGLT2 inhibitors in delaying CKD progression.¹⁸

Finally, Jamil et al. (2022) conducted a meta-analysis of 27,520 patients and demonstrated that SGLT2 inhibitors significantly reduced major adverse cardiovascular events, all-cause mortality, and HbA1c levels, while also lowering the risk of acute kidney injury and hyperkalemia. While our study did not assess cardiovascular or safety endpoints, the consistent preservation of eGFR and reduction in

proteinuria in our cohort align with the broader evidence base of SGLT2 inhibitors offering both renal and systemic benefits.¹⁹

This study directly compared SGLT2 inhibitors with standard therapy in slowing CKD progression. A well-defined sample of 120 patients provided reliable data for statistical analysis. Multiple renal parameters including eGFR and proteinuria were assessed at baseline and follow-up. However, the follow-up duration of six months was relatively short for long-term CKD outcomes. The study was single-center, which may limit generalizability to wider populations. Adverse events and cardiovascular outcomes were not comprehensively assessed.

CONCLUSION

SGLT2 inhibitors were more effective than standard therapy in slowing the progression of CKD. They showed better preservation of eGFR and greater reduction in proteinuria over six months.

These findings highlight the potential of SGLT2 inhibitors as a preferred treatment option in CKD management.

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